

A CASE STUDY ON VICHARCHIKA

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ABSTRACT

Disorders affecting skin has a great impaction in the quality of life. Eczema in its various forms is by far the commonest skin disorder. Aetiology of eczema is complex; fatigue and emotional stress may predispose to an attack which is partly determined by external factors. In other words, emotional factors are apparently solely responsible. They can play a large part in perpetuation of an eruption which was initially exogenous. The presentation of Eczema may be compared with *Vicharchika*. This case report describes a female patient of age 56 with complaints of blackish discolouration of hands and legs with itching for 4 years. Considering all the parameters treatment was planned with oral and external medications. Here the treatment of *Vicharchika* points towards an affordable remedy which can be effectively be provided by *Ayurveda*. The results were permanent and was good evidence for the

application of principles of Ayurveda.

KEYWORDS: *Vicharchika*, Eczema, Rasayana, Stress.

INTRODUCTION

Skin is considered as the essential part of overall identity; moreover it's the largest organ of the human body. Various abnormalities in the body is often showed as a sign through the skin. Multiple references of formulations are mentioned for the skin health since ancient times for both therapeutic and cosmetic purposes. People suffering from any disorder of skin often find themselves in a situation where the physical appearance is at odds with their own self image. Itching is the predominant symptom of eczema and may be severe.^[1] Rubbing and scratching

may produce lichenification- thickening of skin with exaggeration of normal skin marking and often some pigmentation.^[2] Secondary infection, unwise treatment or recurrent attacks can modify the basic changes of the eczema reaction.^[3]

Sweat retention is often an important factor. Sweating of thermal or emotional origin provokes crisis of intense irritation in areas where partial or complete sweat duct occlusion has been produced by pre-existing inflammatory epidermal lesions. Endocrine and nutritional factors play a poorly understood role in some cases.^[4]

The disease *Kushta* is characterised by discoloration of skin along with loss of tactile sensation, rashes, excessive or no perspiration. Chronicity of the disease develops deformity. Classification of *Kushta* is based on *dosha pradhanyata*.

Due to consumption of *Nidana Vatadi Dosha* gets aggravated and simultaneously the vitiations effect the *Rasa Rakta Mamsa* and *Ambu*. Varieties of *Kushta* is observed with the predominance *Dosha*.

Vicharchika is one among 11 *Kshudra Kushta* predominant of *Kapha dosha*.

It is diagnosed by following clinical features: Skin eruptions are black in colour having excessive exudation and itching; sometimes being painful.

CASE REPORT

On 28th September 2024 a Hindu female 56year old, nondiabetic, not a known case of hypertension, visited Out Patient department of Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara College of Ayurveda Udupi, with the complaints stated below.

Chief complaints

Complaints of itching over hands and legs along with dry lesions since 4 years.

History of present illness

Patient was said to be asymptomatic 3 years back. Gradually she noticed diffuse lesions over the palm region associated with severe itching and watery discharge some days associated with pain. She had taken the treatment from a general physician but found no complete relief, then she came here for further management.

Personal history

Patient is a worker in a cement factory with a mixed type of dietary habit.

General examination

General condition- Good

RS- NAD

CVS- S1 S2 NAD; No added sounds

CNS- NAD

P/A- Soft

BP- 130/90mmHg

Pulse- 76/min

Moderately built with no other systemic illness

Prakriti- Kapha- Vataja

Vikriti- Kapha-Vata

Sara- Madhyama

Samhanana- Madhyama

Pramana- Madhyama

Satwa- Madhyama

Satmya- Madhyama

Vyayama shakti- Madhyama

Local examination

Type of lesion was papule and scaly lesions

Colour was blackish and skin at the site of lesions were thick.

- *Dosha-* Kapha Pradhana Tridosha
- *Dushya-* Twak, Ratka
- *Agni-* Mandagni
- *Srotas-* Rakta vaha srotas
- *Nidana-* Virudhaahara, Vegadharana, Divaswapna, Atisevana of Dadhi, Matsya.

Samprapti

Due to above said *Nidana*; it vitiates the *Dushya* like *Twak*, *Rakta* resulting in the *Lakshana* like *Kandu*, *Kotha*, *Srava*, *Pidaka*.

Diagnosis- *Vicharchika*

Treatment**Oral Medications**

Guduchi Capsule	1-1-1 x 30 days; After food
Shodak syrup	10ml- 10ml- 10ml x 30 days; After food
Mahakalyanaka Ghrita	5ml- 0 -0 x 30 days empty stomach

External Medications

D-Sora soap for bathing
Siddharthaka snana choorna
Cutfar ointment.

Special note- Patient is advised to take light food throughout the treatment period, avoid *Nidana* and maintain proper hygiene in the working environment.

Table 1: Outcomes.

Parameter	Before treatment	15 th day of treatment	30 th day of treatment
Blackish discolouration	Present	Slightly reduced	Reduced
Lichenification	Present	Present	Slightly reduced
Itching	Present	Reduced	Reduced
Papules	Absent	Absent	Absent

Medicines were continued for 1 month again after the 30th day follow-up.

Figure 2: 15th day of treatment.**DISCUSSION**

Eczema is an auto immune condition which when correlated with *Vicharchika* is a disorder with vitiation of *Kapha Pradhana Dosha*. Our *Acharya* has considered this under *Kshudra Kushta*. Even though there is *Kapha* predominance in this condition there is vitiation of all other dosha in its subtle form. The diseases effecting skin affects the quality of life of that individual. Skin being the largest organ of the human body covering externally depicts the internal health of one's body. In Eczema the epidermal fluid loss results in the increased susceptibility to skin reactions which in turn is the result of poor lipid barrier of skin resulting in decreased protection from harmful substances.^[5] Hence treatment of skin disorders in would most of the time need both internal and external medications. Vagbhata acharya mentions about the importance of using *Rasayana* in treating the diseases that are difficult to cure otherwise. Psychological stress exacerbate the symptoms of Eczema.^[6] Mahakalyanaka *Ghritha* is *Deepana*, *Pachana Medhya* and *Kushtahara*; contains *Sariva*, *Haridra*, *Manjishta* etc that helps in the reduction of *Shyavavarnatha*; also it is good in overcoming the itching caused by long term exposure of local irritants as in this case the patient is working in a cement factory. *Vipadikahara malahara* and *Jatyadi taila* in cutfar ointment helps in penetrating into the skin providing a *Ropana* and *Snehana* action. *Mahamanjishtadi Kashaya* containing *Guduchi*, *Manjishta*, *Nimba*, *Sariva*, *Karanja* etc is *Kushtahara* and corrects the *Raktadushti*. *Guduchi* capsule act as an immunomodulator decreasing the incidence of further inflammation to the leisions.^[7] *Siddharthaka Snana Choorna* is *Twak Doshahara* and D-sora soap helps in the healing and protection of skin.

CONCLUSION

Vranashodaka, *Ropaka*, *Medhya* and *Rasayana* properties of specified drugs showed an excellent result in *Vicharchika*. In the present case the patient has only been treated with the *Shamana Chikitsa* and has given a regression of disease. *Pitta* and *Vata Dosha* were also given equal importance along with *Kapha Dosha*. *Pathya- Apathya* considerations are very important for the fast recovery into a normal skin.

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